

Pilot Evaluation 7: Team Science

Final Version

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Summary

The Team Science pilot project focused on developing and experimenting with an innovative format for enriching the human capital development framework of the Una Europa Alliance in relation to the issue of Team Science. More precisely, the pilot centred on developing a joint MOOC on Team Science and a practically-oriented workshop for researchers and professional staff members. The MOOC and the workshop together constitute an experimental format for future skill development and for an Una Europa certification framework, but one that is transferrable and scalable to other European University alliances. At its core, the pilot aimed to emphasise the importance and intricacies of interdisciplinary collaboration in research. In meeting these aims, the pilot project strategically engaged with multiple transformation modules, including: anticipation of research impact, promotion of R&I standards, broadening the scope of R&I activities, stakeholder engagement in R&I decision-making, and advocacy for Open Science.

The pilot consisted of six distinct stages: identification of the joint team for developing the format, development of the content of the MOOC as well as the workshop, recording of the MOOC, participation in the MOOC by selected researchers/professional staff members, the online workshop, and collecting feedback. The creation of a MOOC tailored for researchers and professionals marked a significant **outcome** in standardising interdisciplinary team science. The course not only provided knowledge on the subject but also demonstrated collaborative principles through its structure and delivery.

The pilot project further developed the comprehensive understanding of Team Science and its importance – a topic which is very much neglected in skills development programs and HR policies. The MOOC has played a pivotal role in translating and synthesising Una.Resin's knowledge and innovations into an accessible format. By making this course more broadly available, the pilot will ensure that the synthesised knowledge reaches a broader audience, further amplifying its impact. The potential for influence is vast. For example, the pilot emphasises the need for interdisciplinary approaches that, in turn, may inform policies related to research collaboration and standardisation.

The **lessons learned** from implementing the pilot underline the need to pool expertise and support at the Alliance level, as well as facilitate collaborative environments and address often overlooked areas of skills development. By integrating the lessons learnt, future initiatives can be structured to maximise the effectiveness and reach of professional development programs within the Alliance.

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The idea behind the Team Science pilot action was to develop and experiment with an innovative format for enriching the human capital development framework of the Una Europa University Alliance in relation to the issue of Team Science. The pilot aimed to develop a joint Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) on Team Science and a practically-oriented workshop for researchers and professional staff members. The MOOC and workshop together constitute

an experimental format for the future skills development and certification framework of Una Europa, but transferrable and scalable to other European University Alliances. The selection of this topic for the pilot resulted from previous work in Una.Resin, which exemplified how the issue of Team Science is not well-understood among researchers, and that universities do not provide sufficient training in this area.

The Team Science pilot was designed to provide knowledge on interdisciplinary team science, as well as demonstrate the principles of collaborative research in its structure and delivery. The target groups for the project were researchers and professional staff, specifically those at the forefront of research teams. The pilot includes all the critical facets of team science, from the psychological aspects of collaborative endeavours to the practical challenges of leading research teams. The Team Science pilot strategically engaged with the following transformation modules:

- **Anticipation of Research Impact:** With focus modules like "Team science and its science", the pilot delved into the potential implications of collaborative research, such as understanding cognitive bias.
- **Promotion of R&I Standards:** By emphasising leadership and team management aspects, the pilot emphasised aligning research operations with ethical standards and societal considerations.
- **Broadening the Scope of R&I Activities:** The pilot advocated for expansive research collaboration beyond traditional settings, emphasising stakeholder engagement and collaborative models like the quadruple helix.
- **Stakeholder Engagement in R&I Decision Making:** Ensuring a comprehensive and democratic approach to knowledge creation by strengthening ties between academic institutions and external entities.
- **Advocacy for Open Science:** With an emphasis on transparency in research funding, the pilot underscored the value of making scientific outputs accessible and transparent.

The Team Science MOOC and the following workshop were focused on several challenges connected to the broader theme of effective interdisciplinary collaboration:

- The nuances of leading diverse research teams and managing inherent complexities.
- The limitations posed by rigid academic boundaries, which often deter cross-border collaboration.
- A lack of comprehensive stakeholder engagement, potentially narrowing the scope and applicability of research endeavours.
- Limited understanding and application of Open Science principles, especially in funding and dissemination of research.

The Team Science pilot, culminating with the Team Science MOOC, has made progress towards addressing the targeted transformation modules. It has exposed the complexities and opportunities of interdisciplinary collaboration, creating a blueprint for future initiatives. The multi-staged approach, starting from the creation of the MOOC to its wide-scale dissemination and the collecting of feedback, ensures a comprehensive engagement with the EC transformation modules. The envisaged Una Europa certification system further amplifies the pilot's commitment to institutional transformation, aiming to set collaborative research benchmarks.

The pilot project sought to initiate desired institutional change by:

- Developing Gender Equality Plans/measures.
- Developing material for integration of science and society in curricula (e.g., covering STEM, public engagement, ethics, gender).
- Helping uphold human rights and high general ethical standards, by adoption, development and/or implementation of codes of conduct, ethical review, etc.
- Developing activities to anticipate the potential social, environmental, and economic impacts of research (e.g., risk assessment, threat assessment, foresight, impact assessment, gender analysis).
- Developing a Social Corporate Responsibility dimension to foster responsible innovation.
- Helping develop R&I standards that enhance social responsibility, inclusiveness, and sustainability of R&I processes and products.
- Enlarging the scope of R&I activities by fostering informal science education (museums, science centres), promoting citizen science, and engaging civil society actors and citizens.
- Engaging with multiple stakeholders for R&I decision-making at local, national, and regional level of the EU and/or at the global level.
- Fostering Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.).

To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are: universities in general, research performing organisation, public authorities, international organisations, researchers, businesses and industry engaged in R&D, citizens, and NGOs. With the beneficiaries of the pilot being: researchers, external users (academic and non-academic), citizens, other universities, and European University Alliances.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

This pilot was structured in six distinct stages:

- Stage 1: Identification of the joint team for developing the format (specialists in: psychology, philosophy, etc.).
- Stage 2: Development of the content of the MOOC as well as the workshop.
- Stage 3: Recording of the MOOC.
- Stage 4: Participation in the MOOC by selected researchers/professional staff members.
- Stage 5: The online workshop.
- Stage 6: Collecting feedback.

The project curriculum was collaboratively designed to provide a comprehensive insight into interdisciplinary team science, mirroring collaborative principles both in content and delivery. Additionally, the broader ambition was to initiate a certification system endorsed by Una Europa. This certification seeks to recognise the expertise of researchers and standardise the knowledge acquired in interdisciplinary team science, resonating with the commitment of Una Europa and the larger European University Alliance to advocate for collaborative research standards.

Various sources of data were employed throughout the pilot. Initially, participation metrics were gauged upon the introduction in the MOOC to the Copernicus College platform.

Subsequent to this, feedback played an essential role. An online workshop was orchestrated where participants dissected the MOOC's content, critically reflecting on its applicability and relevance in their research domains. Professor Mateusz Hohol's presentation (UJ), centred around team science's cognitive elements, further facilitated in-depth discussions and feedback. This multi-pronged feedback mechanism allowed for a comprehensive understanding of both stakeholder experiences and the course's impact.

The Research Careers and Culture Cluster (RCCC) involvement was imperative to ensuring representation from all collaborating institutions, overseeing feedback mechanisms, and strategising the pilot's future trajectory, especially in aligning with the broader objectives of the Una.Resin project.

One of the issues faced in creating the Team Science MOOC was the identification of appropriate specialists to lead and contribute to the course, since there are no virtual mechanisms in place in Una Europa to support facilitation. Moreover, the initial budget did not cover the costs of recording the MOOCs. Thus, forcing the organisers to seek additional funding, external to Una.Resin, to meet the production needs.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

The Team Science pilot project aimed to emphasise the importance and intricacies of interdisciplinary collaboration in research. The creation of the MOOC, tailored for researchers and professionals, marked a significant step in standardising interdisciplinary team science. The course not only provided knowledge on the subject but also demonstrated collaborative principles through its structure and delivery. The pilot's most important outcomes are:

- The MOOC (or rather, pre-MOOC) was recorded and tested, with feedback on what to improve.
- We tested the combination of a "theoretical" MOOC and "practical" workshop, and collected feedback on how to improve it.
- Good experience in collaboration on such a format with colleagues from different universities was obtained. The accumulated knowledge of specialists from various universities made it easier to develop a comprehensive MOOC; their various points of view contributed to making it better.
- Useful experience in generating feedback was acquired, with various points of view from different universities making the feedback even more useful.
- We further developed the comprehensive understanding and importance of Team Science – a topic which is very much neglected in skill development programs and HR policies.

The MOOC has played a pivotal role in translating and synthesising Una.Resin's knowledge and innovations into an accessible format. Modules like "Anticipation of Research Impact" and "Promotion of R&I Standards" not only convey the project's core values, but also ensure that participants are well-equipped with the latest interdisciplinary research methodologies. By making this course more broadly available, the pilot will ensure that the synthesised knowledge reaches a broader audience, further amplifying its impact.

While the immediate uptake of the pilot project's outcomes by decision-makers at institutional, national, and EU levels might still be in its nascent stages, the potential for influence is vast.

The pilot could inform policies related to research collaboration and standardisation, emphasising the need for interdisciplinary approaches. Based on this the pilot, we anticipate a future, positive shift in the perception and endorsement of collaborative research endeavours across various decision-making platforms.

Lessons learnt

By integrating the lessons learnt, future initiatives can be structured to maximise the effectiveness and reach of professional development programs within the Alliance. The lessons learnt are as follows:

- Expertise collaboration: Pooling of expertise within the Alliance helps to develop comprehensive educational and skills-development tools and materials.
- Targeted skill focus: Addressing often overlooked areas of skill development offers valued growth opportunities for researchers and professional staff.
- Collaborative integration: Facilitating collaborative environments, such as practical workshops, where researchers and professional staff can coalesce, has been crucial. This approach fosters a unified understanding and application of skills in the development programs.
- Alliance support: The development of substantial projects like MOOCs signals a need for enhanced support at the Alliance level. Effective backing endorsement can significantly streamline the process and the necessary resources for MOOC development and implementation.

Recommendations for the future

Adopting the following recommendations could significantly elevate the effectiveness and appeal of future skill development initiatives, leading to more adept and versatile research teams:

- Model exploration: Continued experimentation with the integrated format of MOOCs paired with workshops is advised, which is promising for future skills development programs and accompanying certification processes.
- Inclusive development: The recommendation is to inclusively involve both researchers and professional staff in the creation and refinement of skills development programs. Their joint efforts can yield a more holistic and pragmatic educational approach.
- Collaborative participation: Encourage and facilitate the simultaneous participation of researchers and professional staff in these programs. Such cross-functional engagement can enhance learning experiences and foster a more collaborative research culture.
- Specialised focus: Prioritising underrepresented areas of skill development could fill existing gaps and meet the latent needs within the research community, enhancing the overall competency framework.
- Team Science enhancement: There is a need to expand and enrich programs that specifically bolster team science skills. These are essential in navigating the interdisciplinary demands of contemporary research endeavours.